

Teaching CFD as a Pedagogy for Architectural Design: A qualitative study based on interviews

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ABSTRACT: The goal of this study is to investigate the academic efforts to apply Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) in architectural design. CFD refers to a computational method for predicting the movement of fluid. Since airflow is an important issue in architecture, CFD can be a helpful tool in architectural design. Specifically, the benefit of using CFD can be maximized if it can be used from the beginning of the design process. However, the complexity of CFD has been a barrier to be utilized in the early stages of design. Although the development of new software made CFD more accessible for architectural designers, it caused another problem of blind users who cannot interpret the simulation results. With a qualitative and interview-based research method, this study explores the current position of CFD in architectural design education. Former instructors and students of two CFD courses offered at two design-oriented architecture programs in the US participated in the interviews. Through the interviews, this study questions the future direction of CFD for architectural design education.

KEYWORDS: CFD, Architecture, Design, Education, Interview

1. INTRODUCTION

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) refers to computational methods to predict the movement of fluid. Due to its efficiency, CFD has been widely used in the engineering fields since the 1970s. It has a great potential in the architectural field as well since airflow has been an important issue in architectural design. Moreover, the shape and the interior of buildings have become complex these days, thus, it is becoming hard to predict airflow in and around a building. Although CFD can be helpful to predict airflow in relation with architectural design, the CFD users in the building industry tend to be limited to researchers or consultant engineers rather than architectural designers in general. It has been due to the software license cost and the intensive knowledge required for conducting CFD simulations.

Therefore, in the current practice, architecture firms generally outsource CFD experts for the projects having critical safety issues with airflow. In these cases, CFD is a method for evaluating a completed design rather than actively participating in the design process. However, key design decisions are made in the early stages of design, thus, the benefit of using CFD would be maximized through its early application. In response to the current situation, CFD platforms specialized for architectural projects are developed recently. They offer cheaper license cost and user-friendly interfaces providing the features optimized for architectural projects. Although utilizing these platforms is still unfamiliar in the current practice, some architecture schools in the United States offered a course for learning CFD for students in their programs. This study investigates the academic efforts to explore the application of CFD in architectural design and education.

2. METHODOLOGY

Interview-based approach in qualitative research is an efficient way of collecting data since the data comes directly from the person who has the experiences [1]. Due to these advantages, an interview-based approach is chosen for this study. To obtain rich data while maintaining flexibility, the interviews were semi-structured in an open-ended format.

2.1 Data Collection

After a thorough search of architectural design school curriculum in the US, two institutions were found, which offered a course for learning CFD. The instructors and former students of the course were interviewed through face-to-face meeting or online meeting platforms.

2.2 Data Analysis

The obtained data were analyzed in the following steps:

1. Transcribing the recorded interviews
2. Dividing the transcripts into different excerpts
3. Analyzing the excerpts checking both explicit and implicit meanings
4. Coding in keeping with the findings
5. Clustering codes and developing categories

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the data collection and analysis were summarized with the following categories.

3.1 Contexts

Table 1 shows the summary of the basic information on the investigated courses:

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Table 1: Basic information on the investigated courses.

	Time offered	Software	Academic Level	Number of students
Course 1	2006 ~ 2016	FloVENT	Undergrad. 3 rd year min.	15 max.
Course 2	2014	ScSTREAM	Graduate	10 max.

3.2 Limitation of CFD

The participants pointed out the limitations of CFD as a design tool as described in Table 2.

Table 2. Limitations of CFD.

Simulation Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Difficulty in the simulation of free-form geometry- Interoperability (one-way process)- Excessive simulation time
Supporting Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Lack of supporting knowledge- Uncertainty of the weather in outdoor simulation
External	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Required computer space- License cost

3.3 CFD as an overview of building physics

CFD is a compound of various theories in thermodynamics and fluid dynamics, which can provide the students with an overview of building physics. Showcasing how the building physics theories interact with each other, CFD can play a role as a connection point of those theories.

3.4 CFD as a virtual lab for building science education

Visualization is one of the key concepts of CFD. Visualization quickly catches the students' attention and show fluid flow and temperature distribution without the equations. Therefore, students could experiment their learnings in this virtual lab and ultimately have a better understanding of building science.

3.5 Misleading results caused by the lack of knowledge

CFD results could be easily misleading because the lack of knowledge could lead the users to enter unrealistic inputs. The alterations in the simulation setting could end up with different results. We should constantly question the credibility and the embedded assumptions for the results of CFD.

3.6 Improvement of the architect/consultant engineer relationship

The interests in sustainable design are growing in the current practice, but still many projects are designed without evidences. Through learning CFD, students constantly question about their hypothesis based on the evidence. This approach helps architectural designers to

maintain a balanced position, which eventually opens conversations between designers and engineers.

3.7 Evolution of CFD

Given the fact that the evolution of CFD has been accelerated in recent 20 years, the future of CFD looks promising. The limitations of CFD are now in the process of being solved. Nonetheless, the users should be aware of the trade between accuracy and user-friendliness and judge what is important to know as an architectural designer.

4. CONCLUSION

The interview participants taught CFD in design-oriented architecture schools as they found problems in the current architecture education. The lack of building science education in academia eventually causes the miscommunications and conflicts between architects and consultant engineers in the professional practice. As the implementation of CFD in architectural education seems to be one of the solutions, CFD platforms targeting architectural designers have been emerging recently. However, this phenomenon brought another problem such as a user having difficulties in connecting "simulation input and output" [2]. The problem raises a question: what is necessary to know? To answer this question, we need to determine the "desired knowledge level of architecture students regarding building physics" [3]. Nevertheless, CFD is a "promising area of future research and teaching in architectural education" [4] having a possibility as an architectural design tool. Since there are not many cases of teaching CFD in architecture design schools in the US, a limited number of participants were interviewed. Therefore, this study can be continued to the similar cases in other countries or in the professional practice.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was funded by Student Initiated Grant (SIG) from College of Architecture & Urban Studies, Virginia Tech. We would like to thank Dr. Mohammed Alshayeb, Dr. Jae D. Chang, and Dr. Jeehwan Lee for their supports.

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